

DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH COMPETENCES OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

F.A. Rahmatova.

Associate professor, Jizzakh State Pedagogical University named after Abdulla Qadiri

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7393476>

Abstract. This article talks about the technology of using information educational resources in the development of professional auditory ability, the training of modern personnel who know foreign languages, various directions in the field of information and communication technologies, information and communication competence, and the issues of developing professional competence in foreign languages.

Keywords: competence, educational process, educational practice, information resources, interactive program, software tools, simulation models, reflexive, digitization of programs, educational institutions, professional auditory ability.

РАЗВИТИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ У УЧИТЕЛЕЙ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ ВУЗОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о технологии использования информационных образовательных ресурсов в развитии профессиональной слуховой способности, подготовке современных кадров, владеющих иностранными языками, различных направлениях в области информационно-коммуникационных технологий, информационно-коммуникативной компетенции, а также вопросах развития профессиональные знания иностранных языков.

Ключевые слова: компетентность, образовательный процесс, учебная практика, информационные ресурсы, интерактивная программа, программные средства, имитационные модели, рефлексия, оцифровка программ, образовательные учреждения, профессиональная слухоспособность.

In the researches of recent years, a number of authors have added the following descriptions to the concept of "competence": integral descriptions of the quality of preparation of knowledge and skills for professional activities, including a new quality connecting the acquired knowledge and acquired skills with the ability to apply them in practice; one of the important characteristics of human activity, the main condition of the integral quality and efficiency of the participating person as a result of education; self-improvement in personal activity, availability of knowledge, skills and qualifications that allow the learner to find his place in society; knowledge, qualities based on the intellectual socio-professional description of a person; the integral ability of a person, which allows for earlier development due to the constant complexity of problems and the increase in the level of success in various spheres of life; the individual's general ability and readiness for activity designed for independent participation in the learning process, as well as his labor activity based on success-oriented education; a person's attitude to competence and acquisition by a person of competences suitable for the subject of activity; manifestation of a person's readiness and abilities to apply theoretical knowledge and practical experience to solve certain tasks; the ability to move even in conflict situations; a description given to a person based on a positive assessment of actions aimed at solving important tasks for society. the individual's general ability and readiness for activity designed for independent participation in the learning process, as well as his labor activity based on success-oriented

education; a person's attitude to competence and acquisition by a person of competences suitable for the subject of activity; manifestation of a person's readiness and abilities to apply theoretical knowledge and practical experience to solve certain tasks; the ability to move even in conflict situations; a description given to a person based on a positive assessment of actions aimed at solving important tasks for society. the individual's general ability and readiness for activity designed for independent participation in the learning process, as well as his labor activity based on success-oriented education; a person's attitude to competence and acquisition by a person of competences suitable for the subject of activity; manifestation of a person's readiness and abilities to apply theoretical knowledge and practical experience to solve certain tasks; the ability to move even in conflict situations; a description given to a person based on a positive assessment of actions aimed at solving important tasks for society. a person's attitude to competence and acquisition by a person of competences suitable for the subject of activity; manifestation of a person's readiness and abilities to apply theoretical knowledge and practical experience to solve certain tasks; the ability to move even in conflict situations; a description given to a person based on a positive assessment of actions aimed at solving important tasks for society. a person's attitude to competence and acquisition by a person of competences suitable for the subject of activity; manifestation of a person's readiness and abilities to apply theoretical knowledge and practical experience to solve certain tasks; the ability to move even in conflict situations; a description given to a person based on a positive assessment of actions aimed at solving important tasks for society.

"Competence" (incl. "competence" - "ability") means the effective use of theoretical knowledge in activities, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional competence, skill and talent. The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological scientific research. From a psychological point of view, competence means "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of conflicts, and has a plan of movement in consistently developing and complex processes."

Competence requires self-development, constant enrichment, search for new information and data, taking into account today's requirements, the ability to search for new knowledge, process them and apply the results in one's practical work. A competent specialist should know how to use educational methods that are suitable for this situation, choose and apply methods that are adequate to the problem situation, reject inappropriate ones, look at the problem with a critical eye, analyze and synthesize.

Research competence is sufficient knowledge, skills, abilities and personal skills used in the process of research activities quality and set of individual abilities [4]. Based on the analysis of studies dedicated to the study of the structure and essence of the research competence that is formed in a specialist trained in higher education institutions, we came to the following conclusion:

- the research competence formed in the teachers of future vocational education is considered to be a process with a complex structure, it is a complex of general cultural, professional knowledge, skills and abilities, as well as professional creative approaches, as a result of which professional and research skills are formed in teachers of future vocational education, to positively solve design, experience and technological tasks opportunities arise. As criteria for the formation of the main components of research competence in future primary

education teachers, the following were based: - a positive attitude towards the acquisition of research competence (motivational component), acquisition of knowledge related to the field of research activity (cognitive component), manifestation of basic research skills (technological component); - on the basis of the analysis of psychological and pedagogical studies, the following indicators of the main components of research competence were determined and substantiated: - the understanding of the initial importance of research competence of future primary education teachers and the need to acquire research competence and apply research skills (motivational component); - knowledge in the field of research activities and their awareness application (cognitive component); - independent and successful demonstration of basic research skills in the performance of educational and professional tasks of a research nature (technological component); - on the basis of the determined components of research competence, their indicators and criteria descriptions corresponding to them, research competence is formed in future primary education teachers.

Relying on the stages of formation of research competencies of future primary education teachers and P.Ya. Based on Galperin's theory of mental movements and the gradual formation of concepts, the following were distinguished as pedagogical conditions for the formation of research competencies: - orientation to research activities that allow the formation of understanding and recognition of the professional importance of research competencies; - involvement of students in research activities aimed at the conscious assimilation of basic knowledge and skills in the field of research activities; - enriching the experience of research activity, which ensures the strengthening and improvement of basic knowledge and skills in the field of research activity. Didactic support for the formation of research competences in future teachers of vocational education, "Research competences in the preparation of future teachers of primary education for professional activity", which includes a complex of problem-research cases, electronic educational resources and a special training course called "Methodology of formation of research competences in students", research assignments it was decided to introduce the methodical guide named "formation methodology" into the process of teaching vocational pedagogy ("Professional pedagogy", "Pedagogical skill", "Pedagogy. Psychology"). The main focus in the formation of research competences in future primary education teachers is to justify the progress and results of their research activities, draw independent conclusions, reflexive evaluation of results focused on skill building. The following principles were used in the creation of didactic support for the formation of research competences in future primary education teachers: ✓ scientificity; ✓ awareness and activity; ✓ systematicity and logic; ✓ unity of theory and practice; ✓ instructiveness; ✓ solidity and thoroughness of mastery. On the basis of these principles, the following teaching forms, methods, tools, and preparation stages were determined, which enable effective implementation of the didactic conditions determined, and encourage the methods and actions in this process: a) forms of teaching: collective, group, individual; b) teaching methods: "scientific discussion", "analyze actual problem" and "innovative project"; c) teaching tools: e-learning resources, educational and professional research issues, g) training stages: - interest of future vocational education teachers in research activity (professional motivation), orientation to research activity; - involvement in research activity; - enrichment of research activity experiences. The use of interactive methods of education and electronic educational resources allows future primary teachers to successfully

complete educational and professional assignments of a research nature and develop research competencies in their field of professional activity. In the process of formation of research competences in the future professional education teacher, the following were taken as educational tools: a set of educational and professional tasks of a research nature, project and selection tasks, tests of a research nature. Educational and professional tasks, in turn, are grouped in the following four directions: logical, generating ideas, modeling by example, reflexive. Research is a constructive basis for the formation of competencies in future primary education teachers,

REFERENCES

1. Turmatov J.R. Criteria for determining the level of formation of research skills in students // Vocational education. - Tashkent, 2012.
2. Turmatov J.R. Methodology of formation of research competence in future vocational education teachers // News of UzMU. Scientific journal of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek. - Tashkent, 2018.
3. Turmatov J.R. Content and essence of preparing students for independent research // Education, science and innovation. Spiritual-educational, scientific-methodical journal. - Tashkent, 2018.
4. Rahmatova F.A. Scientific-theoretical foundations of improving the mathematical thinking of future elementary school teachers // Monograph. - Tashkent: Science and Technology, 2017.
5. Rahmatova F.A. Priority directions of the development of mathematics // Problems of modern continuous education: innovation and prospects.
6. Proceedings of the international scientific conference. - Tashkent, 2018.
7. Rakhmatova F.A. Creation of problem-based learning in the field of creative information // Science and the world - Volgograd, 2018.